

Enhancing Information Retrieval Processes through Novel Natural Language Processing Pipelines

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Abstract—Organizations may find it difficult to engage with and manage large corpora of their own text. Keyword search with filtering options often serves as the primary method for information retrieval, which provides basic access to large quantities of data without any mechanism for extracting the most pertinent information from the retrieved documents. To address these constraints, we propose a novel pipeline that caters to both expert users who have a clear understanding of their search requirements, as well as users who seek to gain knowledge on a specific topic from a set of documents. Our pipeline employs semantic search techniques to comprehend related concepts, synonyms, and the context of the documents, allowing users to search for concepts rather than specific keywords. Subsequently, we use natural language processing (NLP) summarization methods, topic modeling, and paragraph-level semantic search on the top k documents to offer users comprehensive insights on their search results and steer them toward the most relevant information. In testing our approach on publicly available government reports, our search pipeline yields contextually relevant search results, provides information on the sub-level topics present in the retrieved documents, and furnishes topic analysis and summaries of each document for easier comprehension.

Index Terms—Semantic Search, Natural Language Processing, Topic Modeling, Keyword Search

I. INTRODUCTION

When organizations have large-text data containing thousands of documents with hundreds of pages each, the problem of efficient information retrieval arises as extracting relevant information becomes increasingly difficult. Many organizations currently implement a standard keyword search with user-selected filters to query data. This approach limits the user’s search. For example, with keyword search, if a user searches for “Nuclear Weapons in Russia” they will find each of the words in isolation and potentially combined if such a string exists in any documents. Although this search narrows the pool of report options, it is not ideal because it is limited to stand-alone words. We propose a semantic search pipeline that narrows results to be domain specific for context of a search concept. In the case of semantic search, results on nuclear armaments in any Eastern European country may arise since Eastern Europe and Russia are contextually related.

We work with an organization that currently maintains a keyword search engine with filter options for use on long-form text reports. We aim to enhance the searchability of these

documents, ultimately offering users more contextual and interactive search results that go beyond the literal words of a search. In response to the question, “How can we improve the relevance of search results?” we develop a novel NLP pipeline that incorporates a multitude of text analytic techniques.

We focus on user-friendly semantic search. Using the MSMARCO model `msmarco-distilbert-base-tas-b`, we develop a multi-level semantic search sequence that offers quick and contextually targeted results. On the search results, we implement various topic modeling methods to dive deeper into content. We preliminarily evaluate the human-interpreted precision of search results from keyword search and semantic search, and we check examples of our topic results against organization-developed categories.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Generating an efficient query using traditional keyword search methods typically requires the user to either already have in-depth knowledge of the subject domain or the style and information within the documents. Guha, McCool, and Miller introduce semantic search through the semantic web as a mechanism for enhancing search capabilities of a corpus, or in their case the web [1]. Semantic search, as they propose, allows for more complex queries and more contextually relevant results from texts. However, this still requires metadata and ontology to be created for the documents of interest.

The introduction of the transformer architecture in neural networks presented by Vaswani et. al in 2017 takes semantic search one step further by allowing more nuanced search queries to be given by the user through the concept of self-attention [2]. Transformers advance sentiment analysis by capturing the context in which things are said or asked. Unlike recurrent neural networks (RNN), the transformer architecture encapsulates long-term dependencies. Because of this advancement, the end-user can submit queries that are written in a natural language style and, assuming a semantic search transformer language model, obtain more relevant results to obtain the best information from the corpus [3].

Our team builds on these tools by developing a pipeline that takes advantage of new neural network architectures and publicly available pre-trained models as the base for client specific models. These models can be re-trained to generate

updated embeddings and ultimately be deployed within an organization. Computational speed and precision in returning relevant documents makes these types of models superior to previous neural network architectures [4].

Pre-trained models are chosen with the final objective in mind. In our case, `msmarco-distilbert-base-tas-b` is the practical choice for the semantic search task as described in Section IV [5].

III. DATA DESCRIPTION

The data comes from a government organization as a table of parsed long-form text reports. There exist seven columns - report number, report section, objective number, header level 1, header level 2, header level 3, and text. The original data consists of 687,835 rows, or 4,202 reports. Our two primary concerns for determining which data is complete and useful are the presence of a core section, which denotes the general substance of a report, and meaningful words in the "text" column. Reports that do not contain a core section were not fully captured in the original dataset, so we omit these reports from our analysis. We find that most reports that have complete text also have a core section. After filtering the data for these requirements, we keep 70.1% of the original data, 2,946 reports. This is not cause for concern because our methods do not rely on specific text, and the pipeline can be implemented on any text data of the same format as long as document and paragraph embeddings are generated beforehand.

Following semantic search implementation, we conduct detailed data cleaning by separating the data contained in the resulting reports into a corpus, vocabulary, and lemmatized corpus. The multi-level index is identified by the data specific Ordered Hierarchy of Content Objects (OHCO) - report number, report section, header level 1, header level 2, and header level 3. The corpus has 3 columns separate from the OHCO index: NLTK part of speech, token, and term. We generate a detailed vocabulary that is indexed by report number and term, including a column for the count of word occurrence in each report. The lemmatized corpus expands upon the generic corpus, indexed by the defined OHCO and including columns for NLTK part of speech, token, term, NLTK's `WordNetLemmatizer` lemmatized term, and a boolean for whether or not a word is changed by lemmatization. This is also where acronym identification occurs for users who wish to include specific government agency acronyms, from a list of predefined government agencies, as part of their search. Both a list of specific agency acronyms found in each document and their occurrence counts can be returned to the user.

The original, filtered data is used for our semantic search pipeline. The additional corpus, vocabulary, and lemmatized corpus are generated for use in topic modeling, topic matching, and acronym identification.

IV. METHODOLOGY

To parse through the long-text documents, we introduce a semantic search pipeline that first extracts the top k most

contextually relevant full reports, and then performs summarization and topic modeling on the returned reports to provide further insights. To begin, we implement a corpus-wide semantic search, which returns a user-specified number of documents, k reports. For the top k documents that are retrieved, the text is cleaned, lemmatized, and tokenized before going through topic modeling and producing end-user visualizations. When constraining results to the highest ranking document returned by the search, we can proceed with further report investigation. An extractive summarization can be pulled directly from the document-wide text, or a secondary semantic search on paragraph embeddings can yield the top paragraphs, by relevance to query, from the document that are then concisely summarized. A process diagram for the search pipeline can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Methodology Pipeline

Our pipeline is beneficial for both domain experts and those who are exploring a domain for the first time. Newcomers can search for a general concept and then be offered a manageable overview of the content that exists within the given concept, and experts can search for exactly what they are looking for to easily find related documents and their associated summaries.

A. Report Level Semantic Search

We implement report level semantic search as the first step in our proposed pipeline to improve the contextual relevance of search results and reduce the effort required to glean specific information from long reports. We create a semantic search model pipeline using Hugging Face's `msmarco-distilbert-base-tas-b` sentence transformer model, which is an asymmetric semantic search model built for short queries and large documents. The model is specifically trained using real Bing search engine queries to develop a semantic framework for information retrieval [5].

In our approach, we use the pre-trained model to create word embeddings for each document, converting them into dense vectors in a high-dimensional space. These word embeddings capture the semantic relationships between words, enabling the

model to understand the meaning of words in context. Then, when a user inputs a query, the query is embedded using the same model that embedded the documents, ensuring consistency across word embeddings. At the time of the search, the encoded query is compared to the encoded documents using cosine similarity. Cosine similarity comparisons quickly return related documents, providing users with efficient and effective means of retrieving contextually relevant information from large text documents.

B. Summarization

Once contextually relevant documents are retrieved, we implement long-text document summarization on a single document, which reduces computational complexity and narrows the scope of digestible content for the user. There are two options for summarization at this point - summarization of the entire top document, or summarization of contextually relevant paragraphs (determined by secondary semantic search). Our preferred method of summarization is based upon relevant paragraphs, and the description of summarization technique focuses on this method.

To extract the most contextually relevant paragraphs from a report, we use the same MSMARCO model to create embeddings for each paragraph in the document. The same embedded search query is then used to analyze cosine similarity on these paragraphs, returning the top k chunks paragraphs that match the search. K is chosen with paragraph length in mind in order to ensure that the summarization model does not receive too much information and overflow.

Next, we make use of the extractive `philschmid/flan-t5-base-samsum` Hugging Face summarization model from the `pipeline` package to summarize the results from the paragraph level semantic search, with the maximum amount of words set to 300 to ensure the summaries are short and digestible for the user. After implementing the document-level semantic search with the a particular query, called query 1, we find a top returned document that contextually aligns with the search. For the sake of organizational privacy, we do not display the resulting extractive summary, but the returned summary is logical (readable) and allows the user to learn about the query without the need for reading dozens pages of a report.

With the combination of secondary, paragraph-level semantic search and an extractive summarizer, we are able to efficiently deliver the user concise and relevant results from the top document returned from their original search.

C. Topic Modeling

In order to assist users in their understanding of how the documents returned from semantic search pertain to both their query and each other, we employ topic modeling. After a corpus-wide semantic search returns the top k documents for a given query, the text within the subset is cleaned and organized as described in Section III. The corpus, lemmatized corpus, and vocabulary are passed into two Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) models based on `Scikit-Learn`.

The first LDA implementation begins with the use of the `Scikit-Learn CountVectorizer` package in order to create a document-term matrix for the entire sub-corpus. The `Scikit-Learn GridSearchCV` function is then used with Hugging Face to determine an estimate for the number of general topics present among the documents.

The second LDA implementation begins by using the estimated number of topics to determine the weighting of each topic within the individual documents. This topic model comes with the ability to assign a name from a predefined list of topics for each of the topics produced. The predefined list of topics was generated by the sponsor organization as an attempt to identify the different categories found within the entire corpus of documents. In order to match the predefined topic names to each LDA topic, `spaCy` is used to match topics to the top-weighted words derived from each topic. Due to the nature of the semantic search pipeline, the topics produced by LDA are often very similar, so the top several manually curated topic names can be matched to each topic by cosine similarity in order to provide a more holistic topic description.

The topic model produced for each subset of documents allows the end user to visualize the results of the entire search pipeline, which may motivate new searches based on topic names. Figure 2 below is an example visualization for how the topic breakdown for each document would appear to a user performing a search.

Fig. 2. Refined Topic Weights: User Visualization

Another significant way topic models can aid the end user in search relevance is by displaying the top words associated within each topic based on weight. When paired with Figure 2, a clearer picture is painted for which topics correspond to which ideas within the documents. Figure 3 is an example visualization for how the highest weighted words appear for each extracted topic.

Fig. 3. Refined Top Topic Words: User Visualization

Topic modeling visualizations can also be used to relate documents to each other. A keyword search simply returns an unweighted list of results based on word matches, but semantic search returns a list of results with weights that are based on

the relevance of a document to the entire search query. By determining which topic seems the most useful to a user’s query based on returned reports, a user can refine their search further and parse through reports that are most pertinent to their needs.

V. RESULTS

Using the organizational data, we test our document-level semantic search and topic modeling methods.

To compare our implementation of semantic search to a keyword search, we create a precision metric that encompasses how well the returned documents relate to the search query. To illustrate the calculation of precision in this context, we proceed with the example search, called query 2. After running document-level semantic search, one of the five returned reports has a title that directly includes our search concept, which appears to be relevant to the query 2. Conversely, when conducting query 2 using the current keyword method, a primary returned report is completely irrelevant because it uses one of the words in the query in an incorrect context. In this example, the semantic search returned a relevant result, whereas the keyword search did not. However, note that this is just one example of the near-infinite queries we could attempt.

We perform basic by-hand precision calculations on three sample queries - each query is named according to the order in which they are implemented. Because our dataset only includes a subset of the total reports that can be found in the keyword search, and incomplete reports are removed, we limit keyword search results to reports that are included in our subset of reports. This way we compare like corpuses. Queries and search results will not be named to preserve organization privacy. The precision of the sample searches are shown in Table 1, which compares keyword and semantic search result relevance on the top 5 returned reports. Checks denote a relevant result and x-marks denote irrelevant results.

Each sample query offers differing results. Query 1 sees the same performance for both semantic and keyword search. Keyword search outperforms semantic search in query 2, and semantic search outperforms keyword search in query 3. However, these sample results are limited because contextual relevance is ultimately determined by the user performing a specific query. Overall, in our sample evaluation we find that semantic search performs slightly better on average than keyword search. The average difference is likely due to the limitation of keyword search which takes words at face-value, whereas semantic search learns context.

As a check of the functionality of the semantic search and topic modeling, we implement a topic matching algorithm. Given a list of organization-created topics, and the topic models generated from semantic search results, we match the man-made and machine-generated topics with cosine similarity using term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) vectors [6]. We find that the topics found in our search results consistently align with the preexisting topics believed to exist at our organization, which bolsters the relevance of our proposed search pipeline.

TABLE I
SAMPLE PRECISION RESULTS

Query	Results				
	Report 1	Report 2	Report 3	Report 4	Report 5
SS: 1	✓	✓	X	X	✓
KS: 1	X	✓	✓	✓	X
SS: 2	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
KS: 2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SS: 3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
KS: 3	X	X	✓	✓	✓

VI. CONCLUSION

Ultimately, we find that our novel search pipeline and associated dynamic models enhance the search experience by enabling contextual consideration for expert or novice audiences. Topic models provide visual representations of search concepts and acronym identification locates common abbreviations; each may offer insight into new search terms for user implementation. Topic matching serves as a valuable method for checking topic existence and relevancy, as well as a basic check on semantic search providing similar results. Precision indicates that semantic search outperforms keyword search on test searches on average.

Limitations of our work primarily rest in the difficulty of analyzing performance without significant time spent manually reviewing results. It is difficult to attach a numeric value to the evaluation of semantic search results, topic modeling, and acronym identification due to the copious amount of information being processed. We attempt to combat these limitations with topic matching and sample precision analysis, but we recognize that even these metrics require human input for interpretation. Ultimately, the evaluation of this text consistently requires human input, and therefore the potential for bias is introduced.

Future work might explore many implementations and extensions of this pipeline, including interactive topic exploration, an interface or dashboard that a user can directly interact with, and extractive summaries. Additionally, better evaluation metrics of pipeline performance would augment confidence in our work. There are many routes that this could take, including the use of user feedback in order to quantify the relevance of search results for each user query. This is just one example of how future researchers might work to calculate precision on a large scale to generate a reliable estimation of the quantitative difference in performance between keyword and semantic search.

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